

Manana Shioshvili

*Head of the Culture Department
Jacob Gogebashvili Telavi State University
Telavi, Georgia*

PEACE – THE GUARANTOR OF HAPPINESS

Annotation: The purpose of the article is to present the evil of war and the life-giving role of peace in the 21st century. A very relevant topic for modern society is peaceful life. Man is born for happiness, freedom, which can only be achieved with peace. Peace is an indicator of civilization. The more intelligent the society is, the more the society is strengthened in the faith of God, the more it is oriented towards peace, towards the elimination of violence.

Keywords: Peace, Violence, faith, georgi_culture, tolerance.

"Here is peace! Peace to you!" This is the case in Georgia. "Good Morning", "Good Day", "Good Evening", "good night", "peaceful journey", "peace to all" – these and other gracious phrases are used by Georgians... And is there anything more desirable than peace? Probably not! "God's peace, which transcends all minds, will cover your hearts and your thoughts".

The only word where "peace" can be associated with sadness is "farewell", because after all, the semantic characteristic of this word is associated with the violation of peace due to separation.

Peace has been its symbol since ancient times, and it is the most beloved bird – dove. Still in the Bible (Old Testament), a scene is described where Noah frees this very bird from the Ark. With this, Noah wanted to make sure that the Great Flood was over. When the water level decreased, Noah opened the bird's window 3 times. The first time the pigeon did not see the ground and returned; the second time it brought an olive branch; and the third time the bird did not return. So, Noah concluded that the pigeon found a place to live on land. Since those ancient times, the Dove has become a symbol of reconciliation between man and God.

those who rejoice in a close relationship with God also today have "the peace of God that transcends any thought" (Philippians 4:6, 7).

Peace is more desirable and appreciated because the antonym of this word is war! War-destructive and destructive of everything for which a person lives, works, exists, is punished.

Part of the society believes that force should be used to prevent unwanted rulers; sometimes they resort to terror to maintain order and subdue the people. And the result of terrorism is only the devaluation of life, bloodshed, and cruelty. The pain inflicted by terrorism often leads its victims to revenge, which is accompanied by even more violence and repression. "Blessed are the peacemakers, for they are called Children of God". (Matthew 5: 9).

Traditional methods of building peace are focused on negative peace. Even the examples of Afghanistan, Kosovo, Bosnia, and Lebanon prove that these efforts are not enough to ensure sustainable peace. Cultural integration, dialogue between ethnicities, development of social

infrastructure is necessary for the establishment of a sustainable security system. Peace policy should be aimed at creating a culture based on tolerance, cooperation and empathy.

"The Lord will give strength to his people; the Lord will bless his people in peace". (Psalm 28: 11).

"We want peace!" – This expression should be a common opinion of the whole world. No one can beat people united by common sense. It is true that war is foolishness, peace is spiritual calling!

today, even in the XXI century, that the Russian-Ukrainian war is going on is the biggest shame. It seems that we are moving towards development, support, love, and unity, but the reality is completely different. Even today, how many sinless children die because of the ambitions of states – to conquer territories. There should be no bullets, tanks, shells, weapons, enemies, and fire on each other today, if we consider our heads as citizens of the developed century; how many centuries the Earth has endured war, struggle between states and millions of people shot.

The time for calm has come. It is a great luxury for everything to be fine, perfect; the important thing is to want to be close to ideality; love and tolerance must be learned. Enmity is not the beginning of good.

I think people will change everything for the better. It is our duty to correct each other and spend a large part of our lives peacefully.

"A quiet one is better than a waste of time and worries". (Ecclesiastes 4: 6).

Let us avoid evil and do good; let us seek peace and follow it, ("Psalm 33: 14"), for the fruits of the spirit are love, joy, peace, longsuffering, joy, kindness, and faithfulness.

The primary guarantee of happiness is peace. may the Lord of peace himself give you peace always and everywhere. May the Lord be with all of you.

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